

Myth: AI algorithms decide what you see online

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There's more than one myth about algorithmic visibility regimes: one posits that AI algorithms are tools used unilaterally by corporations to control what we see; the other argues that these algorithms are mere mirrors, and we are the ones who control what we see online.

Myth

AI algorithms decide what you see online.

Some say that AI algorithms decide what we see online; others argue that algorithms just do what we tell them to do. Neither idea is really accurate. What we see online is the result of several relationships between several actors and things — users and algorithms but also platforms, coders, data, interfaces etc. It is key to understand the inequality that marks these relationships.

Materials

Folien der Präsentation

SCHLÜSSELLITERATUR

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About the author

João Carlos Magalhães

Senior researcher at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society. Much of João's work explores the political and moral ramifications of algorithmic media and technologies. At the HIIG, he heads an [EU-funded project](#) that is mapping out social media platforms' governance structures, with a focus on copyright policies and automated filters. In 2020, he was awarded a fellowship from the Wikimedia Foundation to help create an open database of platforms' policies.

Why, AI?

This post is part of our project "Why, AI?". It is a learning space which helps you to find out more about the myths and truths surrounding automation, algorithms, society and ourselves. It is continuously being filled with new contributions.